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Central Repository for Digital Pathology

WP5 - Regulatory framework for digital slides and AI-based methods

D5.05 - Report on landscape of guidelines, standards and regulatory requirements relevant for digital pathology, clinical

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Abstract

This deliverable reports on the landscape of guidelines, standards and regulatory requirements relevant for digital pathology (clinical). It belongs to Work Package 5 *Regulatory framework for digital slides and AI-based methods* and shows the result of Task 5.5 *Contribution to future standards*.

The field of digital pathology is embedded in the highly regulated health sector. There are currently many guidelines available, both on national and international level, that can be considered. Additionally, there are numerous standardization activities especially on the international and European level that are related to digital pathology. Especially the standardization activities of the international committees ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 *Artificial Intelligence*, ISO/TC 212 212 *Clinical laboratory testing and in vitro diagnostic test systems* and ISO/TC 215 *Health informatics* are of interest.

Within this report, the focus lays on standardization. In the research process, all together nearly 40 standards of high relevance on laboratory processes, health informatics and artificial intelligence in general were found. This list of standardization documents is provided and recommended to be considered for other work packages within Bigpicture. However, a dedicated standardization project focused on digital pathology is currently missing. It is therefore recommended to fill this gap with an according standard project. Work on this has already commenced.

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Glossary

AHG	Ad Hoc Group
AMD	Amendment
AWI	Approved work item
CAG	Committee Advisory Group
CD	Committee draft
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
CWA	CEN Workshop Agreement
DIN	German Institute of Standardization (ge: Deutsches Institut für Normung e.V.)
DIS	Draft International Standards
EN	European Standard
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FDIS	Final draft international standard
FprEN	Final draft European standard
ICS	International Classification for Standards
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
JTC	Joint Technical Committee
JWG	Joint Working Group
NWIP	New work item proposal
prEN	Draft European standard
SC	Subcommittee
TC	Technical Committee
TF	Task Force
TR	Technical Report
TS	Technical Specification
WD	Working draft
WG	Working group
WI	Work item
WSI	Whole Slide Imaging

1 Deliverable Description

This deliverable reports on the landscape of guidelines, standards and regulatory requirements relevant for digital pathology (clinical). It belongs to Work Package 5 *Regulatory framework for digital slides and AI-based methods*. The main objectives of WP5 are 1) to ensure ethical and legal compliance of work performed within Bigpicture in a consistent and coherent manner, 2) to establish a regulatory dialogue working group liaising with regulatory bodies, standardization communities, and Bigpicture partners for accelerating the utilisation of digital pathology and AI-based approaches, and 3) to create, coordinate, and implement quality control for the generation of WSI data in an “AI ready” manner. The primary objective of the solutions developed by WP5 is supporting the work of WP2, WP3 and WP4.

This report shows the result of Task 5.5 *Contribution to future standards*. The aim of this task is to transfer project results into European and/or international standardization, where possible.

The field of digital pathology is embedded in the highly regulated health sector. There are currently many guidelines available, both on national and international level, that can be considered. Additionally, there are numerous standardization activities especially on the international and European level that are related to digital pathology. Especially the standardization activities of the international committees ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 *Artificial Intelligence*, ISO/TC 212 *Clinical laboratory testing and in vitro diagnostic test systems*, ISO/TC 276 *Biotechnology* and ISO/TC 215 *Health informatics* are of interest.

Within this report, the focus lays on standardization. In the research process, all together nearly 40 standards of high relevance on laboratory processes, health informatics and artificial intelligence in general were found. This list of standardization documents is provided and recommended to be considered for other work packages within Bigpicture, such as WP 2, WP 3 and WP 4.

Currently, there is no ISO Standard for digital pathology and AI-based analysis of (whole slide) images for medical diagnosis, even though digital pathology with whole slide imaging (WSI) and AI-based analysis of (whole slide) images are increasingly being adopted in pathology and on the way to complement pathology diagnostics. It is thus recommended to fill this gap with an according standard project. This standard should be well aligned with, but not redundant to, the standard for the pre-examination phase for the analysis of FFPE tissue for in situ detection (ISO 20166-4:2021).

Accordingly, a New Work Item Proposal has been prepared and presented to the according ISO/TC 212 working group.

2 Methods

For the creation of this report, the research was divided into three parts: regulatory environment, available guidelines and standardization framework. With the latter being the main part, this document contains an overview of relevant technical committees, their scopes and their current standardization projects on international and European level.

To provide a comprehensive overview of current standardization activities, standard research (i.e. a research of standardization projects) was performed using the following databases:

- Perinorm (<https://www.perinorm.com/>)
- CEN/CENELEC Projex-Online (<https://projex.cencenelec.eu>)
- ISO Projects (<https://sd.iso.org/projects/>)
- ISO Online Browsing Plattform (<https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#home>)

3 Results

3.1 Digital Pathology

Digital pathology imaging is an emerging field where examination of high-resolution images of tissue specimens enables novel and more effective ways for disease diagnosis. Pathology image analysis segments massive spatial objects such as nuclei and blood vessels, represented with their boundaries, along with many extracted image features from these objects. The derived information is used for many complex queries and analytics to support biomedical research and clinical diagnosis.¹

3.2 Guideline framework

There are numerous national-level guidelines for the safe implementation and quality assessment of digital pathology to promote the active application of this technique. Those guidelines suggest:

- detailed principles to inform primary diagnosis based on WSI, teleconsultation, and telepathology;
- considerations regarding hardware, such as digital scanners, medical image archiving and communication systems, and image display systems;
- considerations for image acquisition, viewing, archiving, and analysis software;
- strategies for connection to laboratory information systems; and basic principles for the validation and quality assessment of digital pathology systems.²

3.3 Guideline landscape

In a recent consensus by Chong et al (2020), a research of general digital pathology guidelines was developed. For this, major electronic databases were searched from January 1, 2000, to May 31, 2019, for relevant literature on guidelines, recommendations, and position papers published or officially announced from major countries. In addition, all relevant studies validating digital pathology and WSI, including original articles and reviews, were searched. The searched databases included MEDLINE (PubMed) and Google Scholar.

Table 1 presents a list of current guidelines and instructions for digital pathology as based on the work of Chong et al., 2020 (with modifications such as an alphabetical sorting by country).

¹ ISO/IEC TR 20547-2:2018, *Information technology – Big data reference architecture – Part 2: Use cases and derived requirements*

² Chong et al, 2020 “Recommendations for pathologic practice using digital pathology: consensus report of the Korean Society of Pathologists” doi: [10.4132/jptm.2020.08.27](https://doi.org/10.4132/jptm.2020.08.27)

Table 1 Overview of current guidelines according to Chong et al., 2020

Country	Publishing association, center and/or society	Guideline and/or instruction	Year of publication
Australia	The Royal College of Pathologists of Australasia (RCPA)	Position statement: telepathology	2014
Canada	Canadian Association of Pathologists (CAP-ACP)	Guidelines from the Canadian Association of Pathologists for establishing a telepathology service for anatomic pathology using whole-slide imaging	2014
EU	European Commission (EC)	Guidelines on the qualification and classification of stand alone software used in healthcare within the regulatory framework of medical devices	2012
Germany	Federal Association of German Pathologist (FAGP-BDP)	Guidelines digital pathology for diagnosis on (and reports of) digital image	2018
Japan	Japanese Society of Pathology (JSP)	Guidelines for pathologic diagnosis using digital pathology image (clinical questions and answers)	2019
Japan	Japanese Society of Pathology (JSP)	Technical standards for digital pathology system for pathologic diagnosis ver. 3	2018
Japan	Japanese Society of Pathology (JSP)	Guidelines for pathologic diagnosis using digital pathology image	2016
Korea	Korean Society of Pathologists (KSP)	Preparation of reimbursement assessment guidelines for AI-based medical technology (pathology)	2019
Spain	Spanish Society of Anatomic Pathology (SEAP-IAP)	Practical guidelines for digital pathology implementation	2015
UK	The Royal College of Pathologists (RCP)	Best practice recommendations for implementing digital pathology	2018
UK	The Royal College of Pathologists (RCP)	Telepathology: guidance from The Royal College of Pathologists	2013
US	College of American Pathologists (CAP)	Validating whole-slide imaging for diagnostic purposes in pathology	2013
US	College of American Pathologists (CAP)	Anatomic pathology checklist: CAP accreditation program	2011
US	American Telemedicine Association (ATA)	Clinical guidelines for telepathology	2004
US	Digital Pathology Association (DPA)	Computational pathology definitions, best practices, and recommendations for regulatory guidance: a white paper from the Digital Pathology Association	2019
US	Digital Pathology Association (DPA)	Validation of digital pathology in a healthcare environment	2011
US	Digital Pathology Association (DPA)	Archival and retrieval in digital pathology systems	2011
US	Digital Pathology Association (DPA)	Interoperability between anatomic pathology laboratory information systems and digital pathology systems	2011
US	Digital Pathology Association (DPA)	Validation of digital pathology systems in the regulated nonclinical environment	2011
US	Food and Drug Administration (FDA)	Technical performance assessment of digital pathology whole-slide imaging devices: draft guidance for industry and Food and Drug Administration staff	2015
US	Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services (CMS)	Clinical Laboratory Improvement Amendments (CLIA)	2015
US	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC)	Clinical Laboratory Improvement Advisory Committee (CLIAC)	2013
US	Society of Toxicologic Pathology	Validation of digital pathology systems in the regulated nonclinical environment	2013
US	Society of Toxicologic Pathology	Pathology position paper on pathology image data	2007

3.4 Standardization framework - fundamentals of standardization

A standard is a consensus-based technical document that provides rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results, reflecting the state-of-the-art. It should be based on the consolidated results of science, technology and experience, aiming at the promotion of the optimum community benefits.³

The application of standards has many positive benefits for a range of stakeholders, such as consumers, enterprises, policy makers and researchers and innovators:⁴

- Standards enhance the safety of products
- Standards promote the interoperability of products and services
- Standards facilitate trade by diminishing trade barriers
- Standards promote common understanding
- Standards support environmental sustainability
- Standards facilitate the uptake of innovation in the marketplace
- Standards reflect the outcome of research and development

There are several routes to standardization on international, European and national level.

On the international level, there are three official standardization organizations: The International Organization for Standardization (ISO), the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), and the International Telecommunication Union (ITU). They work on international standardization issues, which can be addressed to them directly or via the European or national standardization bodies.

On the European level, the European Committee on Standardization (CEN), the European Committee on Electrotechnical Standardization (CENELEC) and the European Telecommunication Standards Institute (ETSI) are responsible.

On national level, many standardization organizations exist. Some countries have more than one organization, some of them are financed by the government, and some are independent. They all work together under the roof of the European and the international standardization bodies. The focus of this report lies on the international and European standardization work.

3.4.1 Types of standard documents

The work of standardization organizations such as ISO/IEC, CEN-CENELEC and DIN focuses entirely on the transparent development of standardization documents involving an open body of experts. According to EN 45020, a standard is defined as follows:

"A document, established by consensus and approved by a recognized body that provides, for common and repeated use, rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results, aimed at the achievement of the optimum degree of order in a given context".

Consensus in this case means the general agreement of all interested parties, characterized by the absence of sustained opposition to key content. The core objective of consensus is to take into account the views of all interested parties concerned and to eliminate any counterarguments.

It is important to clarify that there are various types of existing standards, focusing on different topics of interest. In EN 45020, *Standardization and related activities - General vocabulary* some common

³ CEN, "What is a standard", <https://www.cen.eu/work/ENdev/whatisEN/Pages/default.aspx>; DIN, "A brief introduction to standards", <https://www.din.de/en/about-standards/a-brief-introduction-to-standards>; The formal definition of a standard by ISO and IEC, https://www.iso.org/sites/ConsumersStandards/1_standards.html

⁴ CEN, Information leaflet: "CEN Compass - The world of European Standards", <https://www.cen.eu/news/brochures/brochures/Compass.pdf>, and European Commission "Benefits of standards", https://ec.europa.eu/growth/single-market/european-standards/policy/benefits_en

types of standards are defined as shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Types of standards

Basic standard	Wide-ranging coverage or contains general provisions for one particular field.
Terminology standard	Concerned with terms, accompanied by their definitions etc.
Testing standard	Concerned with testing methods, sometimes supplemented with other provisions related to testing.
Product standard	Specifies requirements to be fulfilled by a product or a group of products to establish its fitness of purpose.
Process standard	Specifies requirements to be fulfilled by a process to establish its fitness of purpose.
Service standard	Specifies requirements to be fulfilled by a service to establish its fitness of purpose.
Interface standard	Specifies requirements concerned with the compatibility of products and systems at their point of connection.
Standard on data to be provided	Contains a list of characteristics for which values or other data are to be stated for specifying the product, process or service.

There are also differences in the levels of transparency, consensus and approval required before publication, leading to different kind of deliverables both on European and international level as mentioned below.

3.4.1.1 European and international deliverables

The following standard documents are being developed on European level⁵:

- European Standard (EN)
- Technical Specification (CEN/TS)
- Technical Report (CEN/TR)
- CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA)
- Guide (CEN Guide).

The following standard documents are being developed on international level⁶:

- ISO Standard (ISO)
- Technical Specifications (ISO/TS)
- Technical Report (ISO/TR)
- Publicly Available Specification (ISO/PAS)
- International Workshop Agreement (IWA)
- Guide (ISO Guide)

Apart from the Workshop Agreements, that have direct industry representation in Workshops, all documents are worked out in the community of the CEN and/or ISO Members, who in turn consult their interested parties, usually via the means of national mirror committees.

The values that the standard documents derive from the characteristics of their development process, are:

- Consensus;
- Openness;
- Transparency;
- National commitment;
- Technical coherence.

⁵ CEN Deliverables, <https://boss.cen.eu/reference-material/guidancedoc/pages/del/>

⁶ ISO Deliverables, <https://www.iso.org/deliverables-all.html>

3.4.1.2 European standard

The European Standard (EN) is a normative document made available by CEN in the three official languages, English, French and German, leading to full implementation, as national standard, Europe-wide.

An EN may be the appropriate deliverable where there is a need for national implementation and withdrawal of conflicting national standards. The rigour in the development of the EN makes it the ideal deliverable to support European legislative needs, or where the standardization need is focused on protecting health and safety or as support to certification. It may also serve the European regulatory purposes of the New Approach.

3.4.1.3 ISO Standard

The International Standard (ISO) is a normative document made available by ISO in the three official languages, English, French and Russian.

3.4.1.4 Technical Specification

A Technical Specification addresses work still under technical development, or where it is believed that there will be a future, but not immediate, possibility of agreement on a Standard. A Technical Specification is published for immediate use, but it also provides a means to obtain feedback. The aim is that it will eventually be transformed and republished as a Standard.

3.4.1.5 Technical Report

A Technical Report contains information of a different kind from that of Standards and Technical Specifications. It may include data obtained from a survey, for example, or from an informative report, or information of the perceived “state of the art”.

3.4.1.6 Publicly Available Specification

A Publicly Available Specification is published to respond to an urgent market need, representing either the consensus of the experts within a working group, or a consensus in an organization external to ISO. As with Technical Specifications, Publicly Available Specifications are published for immediate use and also serve as a means to obtain feedback for an eventual transformation into an International Standard. Publicly Available Specifications have a maximum life of six years, after which they can be transformed into an International Standard or withdrawn.

3.4.1.7 Workshop Agreements

In order to respond to urgent market requirements, Workshop Agreements are prepared through a workshop mechanism outside of CEN and/or ISO committee structures, following a procedure that ensures the broadest range of relevant interested parties have the opportunity to participate, and are approved by consensus amongst the individual participants in the workshops.

A Workshop Agreement is reviewed three years after its publication and can be further processed to become a Publicly Available Specification, a Technical Specification or a Standard, according to the market requirement.

3.4.1.8 Guides

Guides give information about standardization principles and policies and guidance to standards writers. They help readers understand more about the main areas where standards add value.

3.4.2 Levels of Standardization

Every country participating in the European and international standardization world of CEN, CENELEC, ISO and IEC follows the so called delegation principle. National standardization bodies, such as AFNOR in France, DIN in Germany or BSI in the UK send representatives to the European or international standardization committees of CEN, CENELEC, ISO and IEC to represent their national interests (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 Levels of standardization

An important aspect of standardization work is to ensure that the documents do not contradict each other. The importance of European and international standardization has increased noticeably in recent years. For DIN as example, around 90% of all standardization projects are nowadays carried out at European and international level.

Considering the international and European standardization landscape, the Vienna and Dresden Agreements are highly relevant. Those agreements between CEN and ISO (Vienna), CENELEC and IEC (Dresden) have the objective to carry out work at one level of standardization (where possible), and use parallel voting procedures to achieve simultaneous adoption as ISO/IEC standards and European standards (EN).⁷

The development of Standards and other ISO deliverables is carried out by technical committees (TCs) and their subcommittees (SCs), or by project committees. Technical and project committees are established to develop Standards or other deliverables within their approved scopes.

Technical committees, project committees and subcommittees can also establish working groups (WGs) to focus on specific tasks such as developing the first draft of a standard or deliverable.

Advisory groups, study groups, ad hoc groups and editing committees can also be set up to support the activity, as needed.

3.4.2.1 International Standardization Work

The International Organization for Standardization (ISO)⁸ and the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC)⁹ are the responsible standardization organizations on the global level. The International Telecommunications Union (ITU) is the United Nations specialized agency in terms of

⁷ CEN – CENELEC, “International cooperation”, <https://www.cencenelec.eu/intcoop/StandardizationOrg/Pages/default.aspx>

⁸ ISO, <https://www.iso.org/home.html>

⁹ IEC, <https://www.iec.ch/>

information and telecommunication technologies.¹⁰

ISO and IEC are made up of the national standardization organizations. The ITU, on the other hand, is a special unit of the United Nations, whose 191 member states develop recommendations together with companies from the private sector and other regional and national organizations. Only when they are adopted by normative organizations such as ISO, ANSI (USA) or ETSI as well as by national regulatory authorities such as the Federal Network Agency in Germany do they acquire the character of standards.

ISO has recognized regional standardization organizations representing Africa, the Arab countries, the area covered by the Commonwealth of Independent States, Europe, Latin America, the Pacific area, and the South-East Asia nations. The national bodies commit themselves to adopt ISO standards unchanged as national standards and to develop deviating standards only when there are no suitable ISO standards that can be adopted nationally. In the case of IEC, similar agreements apply.¹¹

3.4.2.2 European Standardization Work

At the European level, based on the EU Regulation 1025/2012 on European standardization, standards work is carried out by the European Committee for Standardization (CEN), the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (CENELEC) and the European Telecommunication Standards Institute (ETSI).

The main goal of standardization at European level is to harmonize the national standards of the member states of the European Union (EU). This includes on the one hand the uniform adoption of international standards and on the other hand the creation of European standards. The European standardization organizations CEN (European Committee for Standardization)¹², CENELEC (European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization)¹³ and ETSI (European Telecommunications Standards Institute)¹⁴ are responsible for the organization of European standardization work. CEN is responsible for all non-electronic activities and CENELEC for electrotechnical standardization activities. ETSI is responsible for the standardization activities in the field of telecommunications at European level.

CEN and CENELEC are made up of the national standardization organizations. The other members are made up of the national standardization organizations of the EU and EFTA (European Free Trade Association) member states as well as those states that intend to become members. In addition, there is particularly strong cooperation between CEN and CENELEC. In contrast, the members of ETSI are directly European companies, institutes and organizations.

3.4.2.3 National standardization work

National standardization bodies publish national standards and are members of the European and international standardization bodies. One example is DIN, the national standardization body of Germany¹⁵. Anyone and any organization within Germany can participate in DIN. All incoming requests are reviewed, and it is then decided by the corresponding committee whether there is a demand in the affiliated industry, whether European or international standardization activities already exist and on which level the proposed work shall take place. Subjects that are ongoing on the

¹⁰ ITU, <https://www.itu.int/en/Pages/default.aspx>

¹¹ ISO, "National, regional and international standards and how they relate to regulatory regimes"
https://www.iso.org/sites/ConsumersStandards/1_standards.html

¹² CEN, www.cen.eu

¹³ CENELEC, www.cenelec.eu

¹⁴ ETSI, www.etsi.org

¹⁵ DIN, <https://www.din.de/en>

European level will initiate a standstill clause on the national level.

If the document is developed on national level, technical committees (TCs) are responsible for the technical input. TCs are open for participation by any expert. They include members of each group of interest such as research, industry, and associations.

3.4.3 Development of standards

3.4.3.1 Development of an ISO standard

International Standards are developed by ISO (or IEC, for electro technical standards) according to the national delegation principle, with each country sending a delegation of experts to represent the national standpoint. This standpoint is developed in national committees that "mirror" the international committees. These mirror committees decide whether or not an international standard should be adopted as a national standard; this is voluntary, in contrast to European standards, which must be adopted nationally.

Figure 2 DIN's involvement in European and international standards committees

International standardization work begins with a "new work item proposal". Such proposals can be submitted by:

- A member of the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), or – in electro technical standardization – by a member of the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC)
- A working body of ISO or IEC
- An international organization that has liaison status
- The Technical Management Board of ISO or IEC
- The ISO or IEC Secretary General

A simple majority of national standardization organizations with an interest in the subject matter is required for the proposal to be approved. In addition, a sufficient number of these organizations must also agree to participate in the work. Only then the proposal will be accepted and the work on the standard can begin. Within two months, a "committee draft" is circulated for voting among the members of the responsible technical committee. A draft is drawn up taking any comments received into consideration.

The draft standard is then made available to all ISO (or IEC) members, who have three months to submit their national standpoint and comments. Within a two-month period, anyone may comment on this draft. The national mirror committee discusses all comments received and submits the consolidated national viewpoint to ISO.

If the criteria for approval are fulfilled during the voting procedure, the draft is then published as an international standard. If they are not fulfilled, or if the responsible working group decides so, a final draft is published. The ISO or IEC members then have two months to decide whether or not to accept this as an international standard. No comments are submitted during this voting period. Acceptance

of the final draft requires a two-thirds majority of all active members participating, and not more than a quarter of all votes may be negative. Ratification of an international standard takes place following positive voting. There is no obligation for national standardization bodies as part of ISO or IEC to adopt international standards as national standards.¹⁶

3.4.3.2 Development of a European Standard (EN)

European Standards are developed by CEN, CENELEC (for electrotechnical standards) or ETSI (for standards in telecommunications). Work at CEN and CENELEC is based, as on international level, on the national delegation principle: each country sends a delegation of experts to represent the national standpoint in the European committees. This standpoint is developed in national committees that "mirror" the European committees. By taking the secretariat of a European committee, national members can play a leading role in the committee's work. It is often decisive for national interests to be effectively represented at an early stage of the development of a European Standard.

European standardization work begins with a proposal for a standard, which might come from a member of the European standards organizations (CEN/CENELEC/ETSI), the European Commission, or another European or international organization.

Acceptance for the proposal requires for CEN:

1. 55 % or more of the votes cast (abstentions not counted) are in favour;
2. the population of the countries of the Members having voted positively reaches 65 % or more of the population of the countries of all Members having voted (abstentions not counted).

Acceptance for the proposal requires for CENELEC:

1. a simple majority of the votes cast (abstentions not counted) is in favour; and
2. 71% or more of the weighted votes cast (abstentions not counted) are in favour.

In addition, a sufficient number of national standardization bodies must agree to participate, after having checked with their stakeholders that there is sufficient need - and sufficient financing - for carrying out the necessary work in the national mirror committees. Only then will the proposal be accepted and work on the standard can begin.

If there is an existing international standard on the subject, it will be adopted unchanged as a European Standard. If this is not the case, the responsible working body will draw up a manuscript for the draft standard (prEN). The draft standard is distributed to the national standardization organizations for commenting in what is called the "public enquiry" stage. National comments are to be submitted within three months. The national mirror committee discusses all comments received and submits the consolidated national standpoint. On the basis of the comments received, the responsible working group can either decide to publish the standard or to draw up and issue a final draft. In a formal vote over a two-month period, the members then decide whether to accept this final draft as a European Standard. There is no public enquiry for the final draft. Approval of the final draft requires at least 65% of the weighted votes of CEN members and at least 71% of the weighted votes of CENELEC members. Ratification of a European Standard takes place following positive voting.

After ratification the European Standard must be adopted unchanged as a national standard and any conflicting national standards must be withdrawn. In addition, a standard that has been developed at international level can be simultaneously adopted as a European Standard by means of parallel voting procedures in accordance with the Vienna Agreement. Such standards are also to be automatically adopted by the national standards organizations.¹⁷

¹⁶ ISO/IEC Directives, Part 1, Procedures for the technical work, <https://www.iso.org/sites/directives/current/part1/index.xhtml>

¹⁷ CEN – CENELEC, Internal Regulations Part 2, https://boss.cen.eu/ref/IR2_E.pdf

3.4.3.3 Cooperation between CEN and ISO

CEN has an agreement for technical co-operation with ISO. Through the involvement of experts in Technical Committees, European and national expertise is being developed and recognized globally.

The Vienna Agreement, signed in 1991, was drawn up with the aim of preventing duplication of effort and reducing time when preparing standards. As a result, new standards projects are jointly planned between CEN and ISO. Wherever appropriate priority is given to cooperation with ISO provided that international standards meet European legislative and market requirements and that non-European global players also implement these standards.

The Vienna Agreement allows expertise to be focused and used in an efficient way to the benefit of international standardization. It is completed by jointly developed Guidelines supporting the practical implementation of the Vienna Agreement.¹⁸

¹⁸ ISO, Vienna Agreement https://boss.cen.eu/media/CEN/ref/va_guidelines_implementation.pdf

3.5 Standardization landscape: standardization activities in the field of digital pathology

3.5.1 Relevant standardization committees

For the comprehensive work on standardization, it is highly important to have an overview of the standardization landscape in the field of digital pathology and AI. For this, the relevant standardization committees from ISO, CEN, CENELEC, DIN and DKE were identified.

In the field of digital pathology and AI technologies, the following committees are of interest:

- CEN/TC 140, *In vitro diagnostic medical devices*
- ISO/TC 212, *Clinical laboratory testing and in vitro diagnostic test systems*
- CEN/TC 251, *Health informatics*
- ISO/TC 215, *Health informatics*
- ISO/TC 276, *Biotechnology*
- ISO/IEC JTC 1, *Information technology / SC 42, Artificial Intelligence*

3.5.1.1 CEN/TC 140 In vitro diagnostic medical devices

CEN/TC 140 *In vitro diagnostic medical devices*¹⁹ is responsible for standardization in the field of *in vitro* diagnostic medical devices which are reagents, reagent product, calibrators, control materials, kits, instruments, apparatus, equipment, or system, whether used alone or in combination, intended by the manufacturer to be used *in vitro* for the examination of specimens, including blood and tissue donations, derived from the human body.

This is done solely or principally for the purpose of providing information:

- concerning a physiological or pathological state,
- concerning a congenital abnormality,
- to determine the safety and compatibility with potential recipients,
- to monitor therapeutic measures.

CEN/TC 140 consists of two working groups:

- CEN/TC 140/WG 3 *Quality management in the medical laboratory*
- CEN/TC 140/WG 11 *Annexes Z related to M/575*

3.5.1.2 ISO/TC 212 Clinical laboratory testing and in vitro diagnostic test systems

ISO/TC 212 *Clinical laboratory testing and in vitro diagnostic test systems*²⁰ provides standardization and guidance in the field of laboratory medicine and *in vitro* diagnostic test systems. This includes, for example, quality management, pre- and post-analytical procedures, analytical performance, laboratory safety, reference systems and quality assurance.

Excluded are:

- generic quality management standards as dealt with by ISO / TC 176,
- quality management standards for medical devices dealt with by ISO / TC 210,
- reference materials guidelines dealt with by the ISO Committee on Reference Materials (REMCO),
- conformity assessment guidelines dealt with by the ISO Committee on Conformity assessment (CASCO)

¹⁹ CEN/TC 140

https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:6122&cs=17AAC27260C1A568EEF380BF3E0FD9101

²⁰ ISO/TC 212 <https://www.iso.org/committee/54916.html>

ISO/TC 212 is structured as follows:

- ISO/TC 212/JWG 6 *Joint ISO/TC 212 - ISO/TC 276 WG: Quality practice for detection of SARS-CoV-2*
- ISO/TC 212/STTF *Spanish translation task force*
- ISO/TC 212/WG 1 *Quality and competence in the medical laboratory*
- ISO/TC 212/WG 2 *Reference systems*
- ISO/TC 212/WG 3 *In vitro diagnostic products*
- ISO/TC 212/WG 4 *Microbiology and molecular diagnostics*
- ISO/TC 212/WG 5 *Laboratory biorisk management*

3.5.1.3 CEN/TC 251 Health informatics

CEN/TC 251 *Health informatics*²¹ is responsible for standardization in the field of Health Information and Communications Technology (ICT) to achieve compatibility and interoperability between independent systems and to enable modularity. This includes requirements on health information structure to support clinical and administrative procedures, technical methods to support interoperable systems as well as requirements regarding safety, security and quality.

CEN/TC 251 consists of two working groups:

- CEN/TC 251/WG 1 *Enterprise and Information*
- CEN/TC 251/WG 2 *Technology and Applications*

3.5.1.4 ISO/TC 215 Health informatics

ISO/TC 215 *Health informatics* is responsible for standardization in the field of health informatics, to facilitate capture, interchange and use of health-related data, information, and knowledge to support and enable all aspects of the health system.

ISO/TC 215 is structured as follows:

- ISO/TC 215/SC 1 *Genomics Informatics*
- ISO/TC 215/AHG 5 *Safe, Effective and Secure Digital Therapeutics*
- ISO/TC 215/AHG 6 *Concept of risk and associated terms*
- ISO/TC 215/AHG 7 *On-going management of ISO 27269 and associated standards*
- ISO/TC 215/CAG 1 *Executive council, harmonization and operations*
- ISO/TC 215/CAG 02 *Advisory group*
- ISO/TC 215/JWG 1 *Joint ISO/TC 215 - ISO/TC 249 WG: Traditional Chinese Medicine (Informatics)*
- ISO/TC 215/JWG 7 *Joint ISO/TC 215 - IEC/SC 62A WG: Safe, effective and secure health software and health IT systems, including those incorporating medical devices*
- ISO/TC 215/TF 1 *Task Force on Quantities and Units to be used in e-health*
- ISO/TC 215/TF 5 *AI technologies in health informatics*
- ISO/TC 215/TF 6 *Process and quality improvement*
- ISO/TC 215/WG 1 *Architecture, Frameworks and Models*
- ISO/TC 215/WG 2 *Systems and Device Interoperability*
- ISO/TC 215/WG 3 *Semantic content*
- ISO/TC 215/WG 4 *Security, Safety and Privacy*
- ISO/TC 215/WG 6 *Pharmacy and medicines business*
- ISO/TC 215/WG 10 *Traditional Medicine*

²¹ CEN/TC 251

https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:6232&cs=179BCDF5F3C53AF099558615A53207584

- ISO/TC 215/WG 11 *Personalized digital health*

3.5.1.5 ISO/TC 276, Biotechnology

ISO/TC 276 *Biotechnology*²² is responsible for standardization in the field of biotechnology processes that includes the following topics:

- terms and definitions;
- biobanks and bioresources;
- analytical methods;
- bioprocessing;
- data processing including annotation, analysis, validation, comparability and integration;
- metrology.

ISO/TC 276 is structured as follows:

- ISO/TC 276/CAG *Chair's Advisory Group*
- ISO/TC 276/WG 1 *Terminology (standby)*
- ISO/TC 276/WG 2 *Biobanks and bioresources*
- ISO/TC 276/WG 3 *Analytical methods*
- ISO/TC 276/WG 4 *Bioprocessing*
- ISO/TC 276/WG 5 *Data processing*

3.5.1.6 ISO/IEC JTC 1, Information technology / SC 42, Artificial Intelligence

While ISO/IEC JTC 1 *Information technology*²³ is in general responsible for standardization in the field of information technology, its subcommittee ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42, *Artificial Intelligence*²⁴ specifically deals with standardization in the area of Artificial Intelligence to serve as the focus and proponent for JTC 1's standardization program on Artificial Intelligence and to provide guidance to JTC 1, IEC, and ISO committees developing Artificial Intelligence applications.

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 is structured as follows:

- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42/AG 3 *AI standardization roadmapping*
- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42/AHG 4 *Liaison with SC 27*
- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42/AHG 6 *Comment resolutions - CD/DIS ballots*
- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42/AHG 7 *JTC21 joint development review*
- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42/JWG 2 *Joint Working Group ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 42 - ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 7 : Testing of AI-based systems*
- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42/JWG 3 *Joint Working Group ISO/IEC JTC1/SC42 - ISO/TC 215 WG: AI enabled health informatics*
- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42/WG 1 *Foundational standards*
- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42/WG 2 *Data*
- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42/WG 3 *Trustworthiness*
- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42/WG 4 *Use cases and applications*
- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42/WG 5 *Computational approaches and computational characteristics of AI systems*

3.5.2 Relevant standards

For each TC/SC/WG, a link is provided to the current published standards and the projects under development in Table 3. Table 3 also gives an overview of the most relevant documents per

²² ISO/TC 276 <https://www.iso.org/committee/4514241.html>

²³ ISO/IEC JTC 1 <https://www.iso.org/committee/45020.html>

²⁴ ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 <https://www.iso.org/committee/6794475.html>

TC/SC/WG. The documents have been selected as relevant for the Bigpicture partners based on their title, scope and ICS Code.

As such, they cover diverse topics ranging from laboratory medicine in general to IT applications in health care technology.

Additionally, two further DIN Specifications²⁵ are of interest:

- DIN SPEC 13266:2020-04, *Guideline for the development of deep learning image recognition systems*
- DIN SPEC 13288: 2021-03, *Guideline for the development of deep learning image recognition systems in medicine*

To provide more input on each standard, a detailed overview of standards is included in Annex I – Relevant standards.

It is however of note that there is currently no specific standard for digital pathology and AI-based analysis of (whole slide) images for medical diagnosis.

²⁵ Both documents were not developed within a Technical Committee, but within a process similar to a CEN or ISO Workshop Agreement,

Table 3 Relevant standards

Technical Committee / Subcommittee/Working Group	Published Standards	Projects under development	Projects of high relevance
CEN/TC 140, <i>In vitro diagnostic medical devices</i>	Link	Link	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – EN ISO 15189:2022, <i>Medical laboratories — Requirements for quality and competence</i> (ISO 15189:2022) – EN ISO 19001:2013, <i>In vitro diagnostic medical devices — Information supplied by the manufacturer with in vitro diagnostic reagents for staining in biology</i> (ISO 19001:2013)
ISO/TC 212, <i>Clinical laboratory testing and in vitro diagnostic test systems</i>	Link	Link	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – EN ISO series 20166, <i>Molecular in vitro diagnostic examinations — Specifications for pre-examinations processes for formalin-fixed and paraffin-embedded (FFPE) tissue</i> (ISO series 20166) – ISO 20916:2019, <i>In vitro diagnostic medical devices — Clinical performance studies using specimens from human subjects — Good study practice</i> – ISO/TS 17518:2015, <i>Medical laboratories — Reagents for staining biological material — Guidance for users</i> – ISO/TS 20658:2017, <i>Medical laboratories — Requirements for collection, transport, receipt, and handling of samples</i>
CEN/TC 251, <i>Health informatics</i>	Link	Link	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – CEN/TR 15212:2006, <i>Health informatics - Vocabulary - Maintenance procedure for a web-based terms and concepts database</i> – CEN/TR 15872:2014, <i>Health informatics - Guidance on patient identification and cross-referencing of identities</i>
ISO/TC 215, <i>Health informatics</i>	Link	Link	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – CEN ISO/TS 14265:2013, <i>Health Informatics - Classification of purposes for processing personal health information</i> – EN 12435:2006, <i>Health informatics - Expression of results of measurements in health sciences</i> – EN 14484:2003, <i>Health informatics - International transfer of personal health data covered by the EU data protection directive - High level security policy</i> – EN 14822-3:2005, <i>Health informatics - General purpose information components - Part 3: Clinical</i> – EN 1614:2006, <i>Health informatics - Representation of dedicated kinds of property in laboratory medicine</i> – EN ISO 11238:2018, <i>Health informatics - Identification of medicinal products - Data elements and structures for the unique identification and exchange of regulated information on substances</i> (ISO 11238:2018) – EN ISO 16278:2016, <i>Health informatics - Categorial structure for terminological systems of human anatomy</i> (ISO 16278:2016) – EN ISO 27799:2016, <i>Health informatics - Information security management in health using ISO/IEC 27002</i> (ISO 27799:2016) – ISO/TR 24291:2021, <i>Health informatics — Applications of machine learning technologies in imaging and other medical applications</i>
ISO/TC 276, <i>Biotechnology</i>	Link	Link	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – ISO/DTS 23494-1, <i>Biotechnology — Provenance information model for biological material and data — Part 1: Design concepts and general requirements</i>

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – ISO/CD TS 9491-1, <i>Biotechnology — Recommendations and requirements for predictive computational models in personalized medicine research — Part 1: Guidelines for constructing, verifying and validating models</i> – ISO/TR 3985:2021, <i>Biotechnology — Data publication — Preliminary considerations and concepts</i> – ISO 20691:2022, <i>Biotechnology — Requirements for data formatting and description in the life sciences</i>
<p>ISO/IEC JTC 1, <i>Information technology / SC 42, Artificial Intelligence</i></p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>Link</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – ISO/IEC TS 4213:2022, <i>Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Assessment of machine learning classification performance</i> – ISO/IEC 20546:2019, <i>Information technology — Big data — Overview and vocabulary</i> – ISO/IEC TR series 20547, <i>Information technology — Big data reference architecture</i> – ISO/IEC 22989:2022, <i>Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Artificial intelligence concepts and terminology</i> – ISO/IEC 23053:2022, <i>Framework for Artificial Intelligence (AI) Systems Using Machine Learning (ML)</i> – ISO/IEC TR 24027:2021, <i>Information technology — Artificial intelligence (AI) — Bias in AI systems and AI aided decision making</i> – ISO/IEC TR 24028:2020, <i>Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Overview of trustworthiness in artificial intelligence</i> – ISO/IEC TR 24029-1:2021, <i>Artificial Intelligence (AI) — Assessment of the robustness of neural networks — Part 1: Overview</i> – ISO/IEC TR 24030:2021, <i>Information technology — Artificial intelligence (AI) — Use cases</i> – ISO/IEC TR 24368:2022, <i>Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Overview of ethical and societal concerns</i> – ISO/IEC TR 24372:2021, <i>Information technology — Artificial intelligence (AI) — Overview of computational approaches for AI systems</i> – ISO/IEC 24668:2022, <i>Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Process management framework for big data analytics</i> – ISO/IEC 38507:2022, <i>Information technology — Governance of IT — Governance implications of the use of artificial intelligence by organizations</i>

3.6 Regulatory framework

When describing the regulatory framework, it is important to note the differences between standards and regulations. In general, anyone can use standards, and their use is voluntary. As generally accepted rules of technology, they can be helpful in liability cases, as they make it easier to demonstrate that one has followed best practices. Standards only become mandatory if they are referred to in contracts, laws or regulations.²⁶

There is however a close relation between standards and regulations, as described through the so-called “New Approach”. The “New Approach” was conceived in the early eighties and laid down in a ‘Council Resolution of 7 May 1985 on a New Approach to technical harmonization and standards’.

It is based on four fundamental principles:

- legislative harmonization is limited to the adoption, by means of Directives based on Article 100 of the EC Treaty (Rome Treaty, now Art. 95 of the Amsterdam Treaty), of the essential safety requirements (or other requirements on the general interest) with which products put on the market must conform, and which will therefore enjoy free movement throughout the territory of the European Union (EU);
- the task of drawing up the technical specifications needed for the production and placing on the market of products conforming to the Essential Requirements established by the Directives, while taking into account the current stage of technology, is entrusted to organizations competent in the standardization area (e.g. CEN);
- these technical specifications are not mandatory and maintain their status of voluntary standards;
- but at the same time national authorities are obliged to recognize that products manufactured in conformity with Harmonized Standards are presumed to conform to the Essential Requirements established by the Directive. This means that the producer has the choice of not manufacturing in conformity with the Harmonized Standards but that in this case he has an obligation to prove that his products conform to the Essential Requirements of the Directive.

Thus, under the New Approach, European Directives define essential safety requirements that are given technical detail in standards. The European Commission then issues a standardization request (called a “mandate”) that a “harmonized” European Standard describing these technical details is to be developed. These European Standards are then to be adopted at national level. Products manufactured according to these standards can be presumed to comply with the essential requirements of the relevant directive and can thus be placed on the European market (“presumption of conformity”).

In general, pathology services work in a highly regulated environment that aims to ensure that laboratories provide a safe working environment for staff and can deliver a consistent, accurate and safe service to patients. The regulatory system may vary, depending on the country and jurisdiction.²⁷

3.7 Regulatory landscape

Regulatory trends and expectations for the approval process and post-market responsibilities shift and evolve, sometimes rapidly, particularly for advanced technologies like digital pathology. Digital pathology products, both hardware and software, are regulated as *in vitro* diagnostics (IVDs).²⁸

As such, the [In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices Regulation \(EU\) 2017/746](#) applies.

²⁶ DIN Standards and the law - <https://www.din.de/en/about-standards/standards-and-the-law>

²⁷ The royal college of pathologists “The regulatory landscape for pathology services”, <https://www.rcpath.org/uploads/assets/4c73cb92-92cb-43fa-9e6098a17c0ea2ce/PathologyRegulationFinal-002.pdf>

²⁸ Kearney et al., Bridging the Gap: The Critical Role of Regulatory Affairs and Clinical Affairs in the Total Product Life Cycle of Pathology Imaging Devices and Software. DOI: [10.3389/fmed.2021.765385](https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2021.765385)

For example, IVDR explicitly refers to software in its Annex I on General Safety and Performance Requirements:

- 16. Electronic programmable systems — devices that incorporate electronic programmable systems and software that are devices in themselves
- 16.1. Devices that incorporate electronic programmable systems, including software, or software that are devices in themselves, shall be designed to ensure repeatability, reliability and performance in line with their intended use. In the event of a single fault condition, appropriate means shall be adopted to eliminate or reduce as far as possible consequent risks or impairment of performance.
- 16.2. For devices that incorporate software or for software that are devices in themselves, the software shall be developed and manufactured in accordance with the state of the art taking into account the principles of development life cycle, risk management, including information security, verification and validation.

However, there are several requirements according to IVDR that are applicable to digital pathology and AI, which would need further specifications how these should be addressed.²⁹

This situation could be improved by CEN or ISO standard that provides clarification on these issues.

The [Medical Device Regulation \(EU\) 2017/745](#) may also apply.

In general, also the [proposed European law on artificial intelligence](#) could be considered.

The project partners should however consult with their local policy and regulatory authorities in developing their regulatory frameworks to ensure adherence to local regulations.

²⁹ Müller H, Holzinger A, Plass M, Brcic L, Stumptner C, Zatloukal K. Explainability and causability for artificial intelligence-supported medical image analysis in the context of the European In Vitro Diagnostic Regulation. N Biotechnol. 2022 Sep 25;70:67-72. doi: 10.1016/j.nbt.2022.05.002.

4 Conclusion

The landscape of standards, guidelines and regulatory requirements for digital pathology is manifold. This report gives an overview of all standards of interest for digital pathology that should be considered further. However, a standard document on digital pathology alone is currently missing, while a clear need for it is identified.

While there are numerous standards, that generally deal with topics such as “pathology”, “laboratory processes”, “slide preparation”, “health informatics” and “artificial intelligence” and should be considered by all partners, digital pathology together with AI-based analysis of digital images poses new requirements on the standardization of the entire workflow to obtain high-quality (whole slide) images and reproducible, qualitative and quantitative analysis results.

Therefore, a standardization of the entire digital pathology and AI-based image analysis workflow and requirements and recommendations for the respective devices including the performance verification and validation are needed to secure the proper quality of the image and the AI-based analysis result for diagnosis making. This standard document should be well aligned with, but not redundant to, the standard for the pre-examination phase for the analysis of FFPE tissue for in situ detection (ISO 20166-4:2021).

Accordingly, a dedicated New Work Item Proposal (NWIP) on “Digital pathology and AI algorithm-based image analysis” has been prepared by project partners from the Medical University of Graz (MUG) and presented to the responsible ISO/TC 212 working group (see also Annex I – NWIP for Digital Pathology). This standard document should be closely aligned to other working groups and technical committees such as ISO/TC 212, ISO/TC 215, ISO/TC 276, and ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42.

The work on this standard project proposal will continue over the duration of the Bigpicture project and it is recommended that the consortium supports its development. This could e.g., be achieved via a liaison to ISO/TC 212/WG 4. Through liaison, the consortium may take part in the standardization process as outlined in Section 3.4 and thus actively take part in developing the requirements needed for digital pathology.

Annex I – Overview of relevant standards for Bigpicture

Table 4 Overview of relevant standards including the scope, link to project and ICS Code

Projects of high relevance	Scope	Link to Project	ICS Code	Technical Committee / Subcommittee/ Working Group
EN ISO 15189:2022, Medical laboratories — Requirements for quality and competence (ISO 15189:2022)	This document specifies requirements for quality and competence in medical laboratories. This document is applicable to medical laboratories in developing their management systems and assessing their competence. It is also applicable for confirming or recognizing the competence of medical laboratories by laboratory users, regulatory authorities and accreditation bodies. This document is also applicable to point-of-care testing (POCT).	Link	03.120.10 Quality management and quality assurance 11.100.01 Laboratory medicine in general	CEN/TC 140 ISO/TC 212
EN ISO 15190:2020, Medical laboratories — Requirements for safety (ISO 15190:2020)	This document specifies requirements for safe practices in the medical laboratory (herein after referred to as “the laboratory”).	Link	11.100.01 Laboratory medicine in general	CEN/TC 140 ISO/TC 212
EN ISO 19001:2013, In vitro diagnostic medical devices — Information supplied by the manufacturer with in vitro diagnostic reagents for staining in biology (ISO 19001:2013)	ISO 19001:2013 specifies requirements for information supplied by the manufacturer with reagents used in staining in biology. It applies to producers, suppliers and vendors of dyes, stains, chromogenic reagents and other reagents used for staining in histology and cytology including bacteriology, haematology, histochemistry, as performed in medical laboratories, both routine and research bacteriology. The requirements for information supplied by the manufacturer specified in ISO 19001:2013 are a prerequisite for achieving comparable and reproducible results in all fields of staining in biology.	Link	11.040.55 Diagnostic equipment 11.100.10 In vitro diagnostic test systems	CEN/TC 140 ISO/TC 212
EN ISO series 20166, Molecular in vitro diagnostic examinations — Specifications for pre-examinations processes for formalin-fixed and paraffin-embedded (FFPE) tissue (ISO series 20166)	This document gives guidelines on the handling, documentation, storage and processing of formalin-fixed and paraffin-embedded (FFPE) tissue specimens intended for RNA examination during the pre-examination phase before a molecular assay is performed. This document is applicable to molecular in vitro diagnostic examinations including laboratory developed tests performed by medical laboratories and molecular pathology laboratories. It is also intended to be used by laboratory customers, in vitro diagnostics developers and manufacturers, biobanks, institutions and commercial organizations performing biomedical research, and regulatory authorities.	Link	11.100.10 In vitro diagnostic test systems	CEN/TC 140 ISO/TC 212
ISO 20916:2019,	This document defines good study practice for the planning, design, conduct, recording and reporting of clinical performance studies carried out to assess the	Link	11.100.10 In vitro diagnostic test systems	ISO/TC 212

<p><i>In vitro diagnostic medical devices — Clinical performance studies using specimens from human subjects — Good study practice</i></p>	<p>clinical performance and safety of in vitro diagnostic (IVD) medical devices for regulatory purposes.</p>			
<p><i>ISO/TS 17518:2015, Medical laboratories — Reagents for staining biological material — Guidance for users</i></p>	<p>ISO/TS 17518:2015 provides requirements and guidance for selecting and assessing the quality of reagents to be used for in vitro diagnostic staining in biology. This Technical Specification applies to the professional use of reagents for staining in biology by medical laboratories, and in particular, to those who are responsible for the requisition and evaluation of these reagents in medical laboratory disciplines such as clinical cytology, haematology, histopathology, microbiology, and molecular biology.</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>11.100.01 Laboratory medicine in general</p>	<p>ISO/TC 212</p>
<p><i>ISO/TS 20658:2017, Medical laboratories — Requirements for collection, transport, receipt, and handling of samples</i></p>	<p>ISO/TS 20658:2017 specifies requirements and good practice recommendations for the collection, transport, receipt and handling of samples intended for medical laboratory examinations. ISO/TS 20658:2017 is applicable to medical laboratories and other medical services involved in laboratory pre-examination processes that include the examination request, patient preparation and identification, sample collection, transport, receipt and storage. It may also be applicable to some biobanks. ISO/TS 20658:2017 does not apply to blood and blood products intended for transfusion.</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>11.100.01 Laboratory medicine in general</p>	<p>ISO/TC 212</p>
<p><i>CEN/TR 15212:2006, Health informatics - Vocabulary - Maintenance procedure for a web-based terms and concepts database</i></p>	<p>This document describes the general requirements on a terms and concepts database. This document also proposes a maintenance procedure for CEN/TC 251, the content, structure and user interface to a web-based terms- and concepts database that will compile the defined concepts with their preferred terms and definitions from the standards developed by CEN/TC 251. These are terms from the health informatics field and not all terms and concepts used in healthcare. It also describes an example of an implementation and ends with a proposal for CEN/TC 251 for the establishment and maintenance of such a terms and concepts database.</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>01.040.35 Information technology (Vocabularies) 35.240.80 IT applications in health care technology</p>	<p>CEN/TC 251</p>
<p><i>CEN/TR 15872:2014, Health informatics - Guidance on patient identification and cross-referencing of identities</i></p>	<p>This Technical Report addresses the issue of multiple identifiers that may refer to the same person. It describes the management of patient identification and cross-referencing of identities and provides some practical guidance for addressing implementation of standards, reports, guidelines, methods, etc.</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>35.240.80 IT applications in health care technology</p>	<p>CEN/TC 251</p>
<p><i>CEN ISO/TS 14265:2013, Health Informatics - Classification of purposes for processing personal health information</i></p>	<p>ISO/TS 14265:2011 defines a set of high-level categories of purposes for which personal health information can be processed. This is in order to provide a framework for classifying the various specific purposes that can be defined and used by individual policy domains (e.g. healthcare organizations, regional health authorities, jurisdictions, countries) as an aid to the consistent management of information in the delivery of health care services and for the communication of electronic health records across organizational and jurisdictional boundaries.</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>35.240.80 IT applications in health care technology</p>	<p>CEN/TC 251 ISO/TC 215</p>
<p><i>EN 12435:2006,</i></p>	<p>This document is intended for use by parties to the design, development, acquisition, use and monitoring of health-care related information and information</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>11.020.20 Medical science</p>	<p>CEN/TC 251</p>

Health informatics - Expression of results of measurements in health sciences	systems. It provides a list of units of measurement to be used in representing values of measurable quantities in health sciences.		35.240.70 IT applications in science 35.240.80 IT applications in health care technology	
EN 14484:2003, Health informatics - International transfer of personal health data covered by the EU data protection directive - High level security policy	This item will provide guidance on the data protection policy which should be implemented by organisations which are participants in international applications which involve transfer of person identifiable data across national borders and which require compliance with the EU Data Protection Directive.	Link	35.240.80 IT applications in health care technology	CEN/TC 251
EN 14822-3:2005, Health informatics - General purpose information components - Part 3: Clinical	This European Standard specifies the definition and structuring of information relating to entities that are commonly encountered in communications with and between clinical information computer systems. Within the scope of this European Standard is a description of components and their use. In particular, these components relate to the following sub-domains: - Analysable objects: including samples, body parts, x-rays and other study products, together with their collection and properties. - Clinical information: including observations, patient conditions, procedures, medication treatment, investigations, counselling plus how these items are organised within a record.	Link	35.240.80 IT applications in health care technology	CEN/TC 251
EN 1614:2006, Health informatics - Representation of dedicated kinds of property in laboratory medicine	This European Standard provides a structure aiding the representation, e.g. systematic terms or coding systems, of dedicated kinds of property, including dedicated kinds of quantity, in laboratory medicine. The structure for representation is intended to facilitate the unambiguous communication of messages containing information about properties.	Link	35.240.80 IT applications in health care technology	CEN/TC 251
EN ISO 11238:2018, Health informatics - Identification of medicinal products - Data elements and structures for the unique identification and exchange of regulated information on substances (ISO 11238:2018)	This document provides an information model to define and identify substances within medicinal products or substances used for medicinal purposes, including dietary supplements, foods and cosmetics. The information model can be used in the human and veterinary domain since the principles are transferrable. Other standards and external terminological resources are referenced that are applicable to this document.	Link	35.240.80 IT applications in health care technology	CEN/TC 251 ISO/TC 215
EN ISO 16278:2016, Health informatics - Categorial structure for terminological systems of human anatomy (ISO 16278:2016)	ISO 16278:2016 defines the characteristics required to synthetically describe the organization and content of human anatomy within a terminological system. It is intended primarily for use with computer-based applications such as clinical electronic health records, decision support and for various bio-medical research purposes.	Link	35.240.80 IT applications in health care technology	CEN/TC 251 ISO/TC 215
EN ISO 27799:2016, Health informatics - Information security management in health using ISO/IEC 27002 (ISO 27799:2016)	ISO 27799:2016 gives guidelines for organizational information security standards and information security management practices including the selection, implementation and management of controls taking into consideration the organization's information security risk environment(s).	Link	35.240.80 - IT applications in health care technology	CEN/TC 251 ISO/TC 215

	It defines guidelines to support the interpretation and implementation in health informatics of ISO/IEC 27002 and is a companion to that International Standard.			
ISO/TR 24291:2021, Health informatics — Applications of machine learning technologies in imaging and other medical applications	<p>This document lists examples of and defines categories of use cases for machine learning in medicine for clinical practice.</p> <p>The developments and applications of machine learning technologies for artificial intelligence consist of 1) data collection and curation, 2) pre-processing, 3) model training and validation, and 4) medicine depending on various kinds of specialty including radiology, pathology, emergency medicine, dermatology, ophthalmology, anaesthesia, surgery, etc., and clinical settings including repeated detection and/or diagnosis, real-time monitoring, and treatment prediction.</p>	Link	35.240.80 - IT applications in health care technology	ISO/TC 215
ISO/DTS 23494-1, Biotechnology — Provenance information model for biological material and data — Part 1: Design concepts and general requirements	(under development)	Link	07.080 Biology. Botany. Zoology	ISO/TC 215
ISO/CD TS 9491-1, Biotechnology — Recommendations and requirements for predictive computational models in personalized medicine research — Part 1: Guidelines for constructing, verifying and validating models	<p>This document defines challenges and requirements for predictive computational models constructed for research purposes in personalized medicine. It specifies recommendations and requirements for the setup, formatting, validation, simulation, storing and sharing of such models, as well as their application in clinical trials and other research areas.</p> <p>It summarizes specific challenges regarding data input, as well as verifying and validating of such models that can be considered as best practices for modelling in research and development in the field of personalized medicine.</p> <p>This document also specifies recommendations and requirements for data used to construct or needed for validating models, including rules and requirements for formatting, description, annotation, interoperability, integration, accessing, as well as recording and documenting the provenance of such data. This document does not provide specific rules or requirements for the use of computational models in the clinical routine, or for diagnostic or therapeutic purposes.</p>	Link	07.080 Biology. Botany. Zoology	ISO/TC 276
ISO/TR 3985:2021, Biotechnology — Data publication — Preliminary considerations and concepts	<p>This document reviews best practices that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) respect the existing standardization efforts of life sciences research communities; b) normalize key aspects of data description particularly at the level of the biology being studied (and shared) across the life sciences communities; c) ensure that data are “findable” and useable by other researchers; and d) provide guidance and metrics for assessing the applicability of a particular data sharing plan. <p>This document is applicable to domains in life sciences including biotechnology, genomics (including massively parallel nucleotide sequencing, metagenomics, epigenomics and functional genomics), transcriptomics, translomics, proteomics, metabolomics, lipidomics, glycomics, enzymology, immunochemistry, life science imaging, synthetic biology, systems biology, systems medicine and related fields.</p>	Link	07.080 Biology. Botany. Zoology	ISO/TC 276

<p>ISO 20691:2022, <i>Biotechnology — Requirements for data formatting and description in the life sciences</i></p>	<p>This document specifies requirements for the consistent formatting and documentation of data and corresponding metadata (i.e. data describing the data and its context) in the life sciences, including biotechnology, and biomedical, as well as non-human biological research and development. It provides guidance on rendering data in the life sciences findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (F-A-I-R).</p> <p>This document is applicable to manual or computational workflows that systematically capture, record or integrate data and corresponding metadata in the life sciences for other purposes.</p> <p>This document provides formatting requirements for both primary experimental or procedural data obtained manually and machine derived data. This document also describes requirements for storing, sharing, accessing, interoperability and reuse of data and corresponding metadata in the life sciences.</p> <p>This document specifies requirements for large quantities of data systematically obtained from automated high throughput workflows in the life sciences, as well as requirements for large-scale and small-scale data sets obtained by other life science technologies and manual data capture.</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>07.080 Biology. Botany. Zoology</p>	<p>ISO/TC 276</p>
<p>ISO/IEC TS 4213:2022, <i>Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Assessment of machine learning classification performance</i></p>	<p>This document specifies methodologies for measuring classification performance of machine learning models, systems and algorithms.</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>35.020 Information technology (IT) in general</p>	<p>ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42</p>
<p>ISO/IEC 20546:2019, <i>Information technology — Big data — Overview and vocabulary</i></p>	<p>This document provides a set of terms and definitions needed to promote improved communication and understanding of this area. It provides a terminological foundation for big data-related standards.</p> <p>This document provides a conceptual overview of the field of big data, its relationship to other technical areas and standards efforts, and the concepts ascribed to big data that are not new to big data.</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>35.020 Information technology (IT) in general 01.040.35 Information technology (Vocabularies)</p>	<p>ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42</p>
<p>ISO/IEC TR series 20547, <i>Information technology — Big data reference architecture</i></p>	<p>This document describes the framework of the big data reference architecture and the process for how a user of the document can apply it to their particular problem domain.</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>35.020 Information technology (IT) in general</p>	<p>ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42</p>
<p>ISO/IEC 22989:2022, <i>Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Artificial intelligence concepts and terminology</i></p>	<p>This document establishes terminology for AI and describes concepts in the field of AI.</p> <p>This document can be used in the development of other standards and in support of communications among diverse, interested parties or stakeholders.</p> <p>This document is applicable to all types of organizations (e.g. commercial enterprises, government agencies, not-for-profit organizations).</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>35.020 Information technology (IT) in general 01.040.35 Information technology (Vocabularies)</p>	<p>ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42</p>
<p>ISO/IEC 23053:2022, <i>Framework for Artificial Intelligence (AI) Systems Using Machine Learning (ML)</i></p>	<p>This document establishes an Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) framework for describing a generic AI system using ML technology. The framework describes the system components and their functions in the AI ecosystem. This document is applicable to all types and sizes of organizations, including public and</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>35.020 Information technology (IT) in general</p>	<p>ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42</p>

	private companies, government entities, and not-for-profit organizations, that are implementing or using AI systems.			
ISO/IEC TR 24027:2021, Information technology — Artificial intelligence (AI) — Bias in AI systems and AI aided decision making	This document addresses bias in relation to AI systems, especially with regards to AI-aided decision-making. Measurement techniques and methods for assessing bias are described, with the aim to address and treat bias-related vulnerabilities. All AI system lifecycle phases are in scope, including but not limited to data collection, training, continual learning, design, testing, evaluation and use.	Link	35.020 Information technology (IT) in general	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42
ISO/IEC TR 24028:2020, Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Overview of trustworthiness in artificial intelligence	This document surveys topics related to trustworthiness in AI systems, including the following: — approaches to establish trust in AI systems through transparency, explainability, controllability, etc.;; — engineering pitfalls and typical associated threats and risks to AI systems, along with possible mitigation techniques and methods; and — approaches to assess and achieve availability, resiliency, reliability, accuracy, safety, security and privacy of AI systems. The specification of levels of trustworthiness for AI systems is out of the scope of this document.	Link	35.020 Information technology (IT) in general	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42
ISO/IEC TR 24029-1:2021, Artificial Intelligence (AI) — Assessment of the robustness of neural networks — Part 1: Overview	This document provides background about existing methods to assess the robustness of neural networks.	Link	35.020 Information technology (IT) in general	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42
ISO/IEC TR 24030:2021, Information technology — Artificial intelligence (AI) — Use cases	This document provides a collection of representative use cases of AI applications in a variety of domains.	Link	35.020 Information technology (IT) in general	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42
ISO/IEC TR 24368:2022, Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Overview of ethical and societal concerns	This document provides a high-level overview of AI ethical and societal concerns. In addition, this document: — provides information in relation to principles, processes and methods in this area; — is intended for technologists, regulators, interest groups, and society at large; — is not intended to advocate for any specific set of values (value systems). This document includes an overview of International Standards that address issues arising from AI ethical and societal concerns.	Link	35.020 Information technology (IT) in general	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42
ISO/IEC TR 24372:2021, Information technology — Artificial intelligence (AI) — Overview of computational approaches for AI systems	This document provides an overview of the state of the art of computational approaches for AI systems, by describing: a) main computational characteristics of AI systems; b) main algorithms and approaches used in AI systems, referencing use cases contained in ISO/IEC TR 24030.	Link	35.020 Information technology (IT) in general	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42
ISO/IEC 24668:2022, Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Process management framework for big data analytics	This document provides a framework for developing processes to effectively leverage big data analytics across the organization irrespective of the industries or sectors. This document specifies process management for big data analytics with its various process categories taken into account along with their interconnectivities. These process categories are organization stakeholder processes, competency development processes, data management processes, analytics development	Link	35.020 Information technology (IT) in general	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42

	processes and technology integration processes. This document describes processes to acquire, describe, store and process data at an organization level which provides big data analytics services.			
ISO/IEC 38507:2022, Information technology — Governance of IT — Governance implications of the use of artificial intelligence by organizations	<p>This document provides guidance for members of the governing body of an organization to enable and govern the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI), in order to ensure its effective, efficient and acceptable use within the organization. This document also provides guidance to a wider community, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — executive managers; — external businesses or technical specialists, such as legal or accounting specialists, retail or industrial associations, or professional bodies; — public authorities and policymakers; — internal and external service providers (including consultants); — assessors and auditors. <p>This document is applicable to the governance of current and future uses of AI as well as the implications of such use for the organization itself. This document is applicable to any organization, including public and private companies, government entities and not-for-profit organizations. This document is applicable to an organization of any size irrespective of their dependence on data or information technologies.</p>	Link	35.020 Information technology (IT) in general	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42
DIN SPEC 13266:2020-04, Guideline for the development of deep learning image recognition systems	<p>This DIN SPEC (PAS) has been developed and approved by the authors named in the foreword. This DIN SPEC (PAS) defines requirements for the development of deep learning image recognition systems. This document gives the conditions, under which image recognition problems can be processed with the help of a Deep-Learning-System.</p> <p>It allows decision makers to gain knowledge about the application possibilities of a Deep-Learning-System and its structure. With the help of this document an estimation about the outlay and use of a Deep-Learning-System can be supported, and a more precise success prognosis can be made.</p> <p>This document gives guidelines for the practical implementation of a Deep-Learning-System starting with processes for data collection over the right structuring of data for AI-image recognition learning to the operational structure of learning experiments and error analyses. This document is meant for decision makers of AI-projects for image recognition as well as for those implementing such projects. This document does not address specific requirements for the fields of active learning, meta learning and continuous learning.</p>	Link	35.240.01 Application of information technology in general	-
DIN SPEC 13288: 2021-03, Guideline for the development of deep learning image recognition systems in medicine	<p>This document gives the requirements, under which image recognition problems in medicine can be addressed using a Deep Learning image recognition system. It allows decision makers to gain knowledge about the application possibilities of a Deep Learning image recognition system in medicine and its structure. With the help of this document, the estimation of the effort and benefit of a Deep Learning image recognition system can be supported and a more accurate forecast of success can be made.</p> <p>This document provides guidelines for the practical development of a Deep Learning image recognition system in medicine, from the procedure of data</p>	Link	35.240.01 Application of information technology in general	-

	<p>collection to the structuring of data for learning AI image recognition and the procedural structure of learning experiments, especially with regard to the increased quality standards and regulatory requirements in medicine.</p> <p>This document is particularly for producers of DL systems and those participating in research and development projects for the application of Deep Learning image recognition systems in medicine. This document does not address specific information about active learning, mental learning, automatic continuous learning and the intended use of the DL System in practice.</p>			
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Annex II – NWIP for Digital Pathology

FORM 4: NEW WORK ITEM PROPOSAL (NP)

Circulation date Click here to enter a date.	Reference number: Enter Number (to be given by ISO Central Secretariat)
Closing date for voting Click here to enter a date.	ISO/TC 212 /ISC Enter Number
Proposer <input type="checkbox"/> ISO member body: Click here to enter text. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Committee, liaison or other ¹ : CEN/TC 140	<input type="checkbox"/> Proposal for a new PC N Click here to enter text.
Secretariat ANSI	

A proposal for a new work item within the scope of an existing committee shall be submitted to the secretariat of that committee.

¹ The proposer of a new work item may be a member body of ISO, the secretariat itself, another technical committee or subcommittee, an organization in liaison, the Technical Management Board or one of the advisory groups, or the Secretary-General. See ISO/IEC Directives Part 1, [Clause 2.3.2](#).

The proposer(s) of the new work item proposal shall:

- make every effort to provide a first working draft for discussion, or at least an outline of a working draft;
- nominate a project leader;
- discuss the proposal with the committee leadership prior to submitting the appropriate form, to decide on an appropriate development track (based on market needs) and draft a project plan including key milestones and the proposed date of the first meeting.

The proposal will be circulated to the P-members of the technical committee or subcommittee for voting, and to the O-members for information.

IMPORTANT NOTE

Proposals without adequate justification risk rejection or referral to originator.

Guidelines for proposing and justifying a new work item are contained [in Annex C of the ISO/IEC Directives, Part 1](#).

- The proposer has considered the guidance given in the Annex C during the preparation of the NP.

Resource availability:

- There are resources available to allow the development of the project to start immediately after project approval* (i.e. project leader, related WG or committee work programme).

* if not, it is recommended that the project be first registered as a preliminary work item (a Form 4 is not required for this) and, when the development can start, Form 4 should be completed to initiate the NP ballot.

Proposal (to be completed by the proposer, following discussion with the committee leadership)

Title of the proposed deliverable

English title

Digital pathology and artificial intelligence (AI)-based image analysis to support medical diagnosis

French title (if available)

[Click here to enter text.](#)

(In the case of an amendment, revision or a new part of an existing document, include the reference number and current title)

Scope of the proposed deliverable

This document specifies requirements and gives recommendations for digital pathology and AI-based image analysis for supporting medical diagnosis. This document focuses on slide-mounted, stained sections from formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded (FFPE) tissues (derived e.g. from surgical resection, biopsy or autopsy) used for digital pathology and for AI-based image analysis, but may also account for paraffin-embedded tissue fixed by fixatives other than formalin.

The following is **within the scope** of this document:

- Digital pathology and AI-based image analysis **workflow (process)** comprising:
 - o the pre-examination workflow to generate slide-mounted sections from paraffin-embedded tissue according to ISO 20166-4:2021
 - o the preparation of slides for digitization (e.g. cleaning)
 - o the acquisition of digital images (i.e. scanning of whole slide images)
 - o the storing, viewing, editing and sharing of digitized (whole slide) images
 - o the selection and application of AI-based image analysis solutions
- Digital pathology and AI-based image analysis **devices** which may be integrated solutions:
 - o slide scanner for whole slide imaging (WSI) image acquisition
 - o workstation with hard- and software components for image viewing.
 - o data storage and management solution
 - o AI-based image analysis solution (e.g. onsite or by cloud service)

The following is **outside the scope** of this document and therefore not covered in this document:

- o the in situ detection techniques
 - o information security and privacy requirements/recommendations
 - o general software-related issues (e.g. software lifecycle management, cybersecurity, interoperability with information management systems)
 - o diagnosis making by pathologists
- Some of these issues are addressed in other standards (for overview see Annex A)

This document is applicable to in vitro diagnostic examinations using digital pathology and AI-based image analysis performed by medical laboratories, in particular but not limited to pathology laboratories. It is also intended to be used by health institutions, in vitro diagnostics developers and manufacturers, and regulatory authorities.

This document is not applicable to other specimen types, such as stained cytological specimens, and sections from frozen tissue or fine needle aspirates. These are not described in this document.

NOTE International, national or regional regulations or requirements can also apply to specific topics covered in this document.

Purpose and justification of the proposal

Technological advances and the increased focus on precision medicine demanding precision diagnostics have paved the way for the development of digital pathology and artificial intelligence (AI)-based image analysis.

The global digital pathology market was valued at USD 736 million in 2021 and is expected to grow at a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 13.2% for the period of 2021-2026.

This is driven by increasing adoption of digital pathology, telepathology, rising incidence of cancer, and growing applications of digital pathology in drug development, complementary diagnostics and companion diagnostics. The (immune)histochemistry sector (using stained tissue sections) is estimated to register the highest growth rate in the market (by application).

Digital pathology using high-resolution digitized (whole slide) images of slide-mounted, stained tissue sections from e.g. surgical resection, biopsy or autopsy specimens, gained increasing relevance in the context of medical diagnostics and personalized medicine. This was enabled by the availability of slide scanners generating digital images with high resolution and information content comparable to classical light microscopes.

Digital pathology and AI-based image analysis can be applied in disease detection, diagnosis and prediction of prognosis to complement the pathologists' opinion, support the identification of the optimal treatment, and the discovery of novel biomarkers and drug targets.

The generation and processing of the digital (whole slide) images for AI-based image analysis requires the modification of diagnostic workflows and needs special medical devices: A whole slide imaging (WSI) system with a slide scanner and a workstation (i.e. hard- and software) for slide viewing and presenting them to pathologists for diagnosis making.

The US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has published a guidance document and approved the first registrations of WSI equipment as medical devices in 2017.

The digital pathology together with AI-based analysis of digital images poses new requirements on the standardization of the entire workflow to obtain high-quality (whole slide) images and reproducible, qualitative and quantitative analysis results. Factors which can impact the quality of the image and the computational analysis result include, for example: i) pre-analytical and analytical factors associated with the collection and processing of tissue specimens and production of stained slides (e.g. tissue fixation and processing, embedding, section quality (e.g. uniformity of section thickness), intactness, size, material and thickness of the slide, staining intensity and homogeneity, placing of the coverslip, air bubbles, dust, or markings on the slide, ii) factors such as errors occurring during scanning (e.g. bar code detection failure, focus failure, incomplete slide scanning (no detection of tissue or missing of tissue parts), improper stitching, line artefacts or variable colour calibration and different settings of brightness, intensity disparity, and boundary intensity during scanning, iii) factors associated with visualisation of digitized images on monitors (e.g. colour calibration, and iv) factors associated with the AI-based analysis (e.g. wrong detection of features or "Clever Hans effect", performance of AI algorithm not demonstrated for features present on a whole slide image).

Therefore, a standardization of the entire digital pathology and AI-based image analysis workflow and requirements and recommendations for the respective devices including the performance verification and validation are needed to secure the proper quality of the image and the AI-based analysis result for diagnosis making.

Consider the following:

Is there a verified market need for the proposal?

What problem does this document solve?

What value will the document bring to end-users?

See [Annex C](#) of the ISO/IEC Directives, Part 1 for more information.

See the following guidance on justification statements in the brochure 'Guidance on New work': <https://www.iso.org/publication/PUB100438.html>

Please select any UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) that this document will support. For more information on SDGs, please visit our website at www.iso.org/SDGs."

- GOAL 1: No Poverty
- GOAL 2: Zero Hunger
- GOAL 3: Good Health and Well-being
- GOAL 4: Quality Education
- GOAL 5: Gender Equality
- GOAL 6: Clean Water and Sanitation
- GOAL 7: Affordable and Clean Energy
- GOAL 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth
- GOAL 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure
- GOAL 10: Reduced Inequality
- GOAL 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities
- GOAL 12: Responsible Consumption and Production
- GOAL 13: Climate Action
- GOAL 14: Life Below Water
- GOAL 15: Life on Land
- GOAL 16: Peace and Justice Strong Institutions
- N/A GOAL 17: Partnerships to achieve the Goal

Preparatory work

(An outline should be included with the proposal)

- A draft is attached
- An outline is attached
- An existing document will serve as the initial basis

The proposer or the proposer's organization is prepared to undertake the preparatory work required: Yes No

If a draft is attached to this proposal

Please select from one of the following options (note that if no option is selected, the default will be the first option):

- Draft document can be registered at Working Draft stage (WD – stage 20.00)
- Draft document can be registered at Committee Draft stage (CD – stage 30.00)
- Draft document can be registered at Draft International Standard stage (DIS – stage 40.00)
- If the attached document is copyrighted or includes copyrighted content, the proposer confirms that copyright permission has been granted for ISO to use this content in compliance with [clause 2.13](#) of the ISO/IEC Directives, Part 1 (see also the [Declaration on copyright](#)).

Is this a Management Systems Standard (MSS)?

- Yes No

NOTE: if Yes, the NP along with the Justification study (see Annex SL of the Consolidated ISO Supplement) must be sent to the MSS Task Force secretariat (tmb@iso.org) for approval before the NP ballot can be launched.

Indication of the preferred type to be developed

- International Standard
 Technical Specification
 Publicly Available Specification

Proposed Standard Development Track (SDT)

To be discussed between proposer and committee manager considering, for example, when the market (the users) needs the document to be available, the maturity of the subject etc.

- 18 months* 24 months 36 months

* Projects using SDT 18 are eligible for the 'Direct publication process' offered by ISO /CS which reduces publication processing time by approximately 1 month.

Draft project plan (as discussed with committee leadership)

Proposed date for first meeting: [Click here to enter a date.](#)

Proposed dates for key milestones:

Circulation of 1st Working Draft (if any) to experts: [Click here to enter a date.](#)

Committee Draft ballot (if any): [Click here to enter a date.](#)

DIS submission*: [Click here to enter a date.](#)

Publication*: [Click here to enter a date.](#)

* Target Dates for DIS submission and Publication should preferably be set a few weeks ahead of the limit dates (automatically given by the selected SDT).

For guidance and support on project management, descriptions of the key milestones and to help you define your project plan and select the appropriate development track, see: go.iso.org/projectmanagement

NOTE: The draft project plan is later used to create a detailed project plan, when the project is approved.

Known patented items (see ISO/IEC Directives, Part 1, [clause 2.14](#) for important guidance)

- Yes No

If "Yes", provide full information as annex

Co-ordination of work

To the best of your knowledge, has this or a similar proposal been submitted to another standards development organization?

- Yes No

If "Yes", please specify which one(s):

[Click here to enter text.](#)

A statement from the proposer as to how the proposed work may relate to or impact on existing work, especially existing ISO and IEC deliverables. The proposer should explain how the work differs from apparently similar work, or explain how duplication and conflict will be minimized

Currently, there is no ISO Standard for digital pathology and AI-based analysis of (whole slide) images for medical diagnosis, despite the fact that digital pathology with whole slide imaging (WSI) and AI-based analysis of (whole slide) images are increasingly being adopted in pathologies and on the way to complement pathology diagnostics.

This standard is well aligned with, but not redundant to, the standard for the pre-examination phase for the analysis of FFPE tissue for in situ detection (ISO 20166-4:2021) and will explicitly give reference to it in the respective chapter on “pre-examination”.

The affected stakeholder category is Health/Safety.

A listing of relevant existing documents at the international, regional and national levels

ISO 15189, Medical laboratories — Requirements for quality and competence
ISO 20166-4:2021, Molecular in vitro diagnostic examinations — Specifications for preexamination processes for formalin-fixed and paraffin-embedded (FFPE) tissue — Part 4:In situ detection techniques

Please fill out the relevant parts of the table below to identify relevant affected stakeholder categories and how they will each benefit from or be impacted by the proposed deliverable

	Benefits/impacts	Examples of organizations/companies to be contacted
Industry and commerce – large industry	Better and more reliable products can be developed with shorter periods of time until reaching the market. Document can provide criteria for product development and help reduce attrition rate in product development	Medical device industry, Clinical research organizations (CROs) Diagnostics industry, Biotech industry, Pharma industry,
Industry and commerce – SMEs	Better and more reliable products can be developed with shorter periods of time until reaching the market. Document can provide criteria for product development and help reduce attrition rate in product development	SMEs building technology and business on digital pathology and AI-based (whole slide) image analysis devices; Clinical research organizations (CROs) applying digital pathology and AI-based (whole slide) image analysis

Government	<p>Criteria/state-of-the-art for accreditations, which are often in governmental hands; fulfilling legislation requirements for IVD development and approvals</p> <p>Contribution to the sustainability of healthcare systems by reducing the number of diagnostic mistakes along the workflow and by improving (future) diagnoses;</p>	<p>Accreditation and certification bodies, notified bodies, FDA, supervising authorities, national governments</p>
Consumers	<p>Reduction of the number of diagnostic errors, leading to improved devices, diagnoses, clinical decisions and healthcare outcomes for the benefit of patients</p>	<p>Patients, medical doctors, patient advocacy groups, medical societies</p>
Labour	<p>Reduced labour cost per project in diagnostics and patient treatment due to standardized workflows and reduced artefact/error rates</p>	<p>Laboratory technicians, directors, pathology staff and managers, researchers</p>
Academic and research bodies	<p>Higher reproducibility of analytical data / study results. Less failed clinical research studies. More efficient use of public grant money.</p>	<p>Pathology institutes, universities, scientific and professional societies e.g. pathology societies such as CAP, ESP</p>
Standards application businesses	<p>Criteria for approval and certification procedures</p>	<p>Accreditation/certification organizations and notified bodies</p>
Non-governmental organizations	<p>Improved health care</p>	<p>Patient advocacy groups</p>
Other (please specify)	<p>Patients will benefit from the proposal because the analysis of di will play an important role in monitoring and prognosing disease and patient´s outcome after treatment. Further benefits include: Improved reproducibility in research, reduced financial losses by improved reproducibility of analytical data; criteria for quality- and value-based reimbursement;</p>	<p>Research infrastructures, research funders, researchers, scientific journals, health care providers and pathology diagnostic providers, health care insurances</p>

<p>Liaisons</p> <p>A listing of relevant external international organizations or internal parties (other ISO and/or IEC committees) to be engaged as liaisons in the development of the deliverable.</p> <p>-</p>	<p>Joint/parallel work</p> <p>Possible joint/parallel work with</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> IEC (please specify committee ID) Click here to enter text.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> CEN (please specify committee ID) CEN/TC 140</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify) To be discussed, e.g. ISOTC212 WG4+WG1</p>
<p>A listing of relevant countries which are not already P-members of the committee</p> <p>Click here to enter text.</p> <p>NOTE: The committee manager shall distribute this NP to the ISO members of the countries listed above to ask if they wish to participate in this work</p>	
<p>Proposed Project Leader (name and e-mail address)</p> <p>Kurt Zatloukal Kurt.zatloukal@medunigraz.at</p> <p>Beth Sheppard elizabeth.sheppard@astrazeneca.com</p> <p>Cornelia Stumptner cornelia.stumptner@medunigraz.at</p>	<p>Name of the Proposer (include contact information)</p> <p>Kurt Zatloukal, M.D. Diagnostic and Research Institute of Pathology Medical University of Graz MED CAMPUS Graz Neue Stiftingtalstrasse 6, Block C, 5th floor, Room 20, 8010 Graz, Austria kurt.zatloukal@medunigraz.at</p>
<p>This proposal will be developed by</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> An existing Working Group (please specify which one: ISO/TC 212/WG 4)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> A new Working Group (title: Click here to enter text.) (Note: establishment of a new WG must be approved by committee resolution)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> The TC/SC directly</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> To be determined</p>	
<p>Supplementary information relating to the proposal</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> This proposal relates to a new ISO document;</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This proposal relates to the adoption as an active project of an item currently registered as a Preliminary Work Item;</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This proposal relates to the re-establishment of a cancelled project as an active project.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other: Click here to enter text.</p>	

Maintenance agencies (MA) and registration authorities (RA)

- This proposal requires the service of a **maintenance agency**.
If yes, please identify the potential candidate:
[Click here to enter text.](#)

- This proposal requires the service of a **registration authority**.
If yes, please identify the potential candidate:
[Click here to enter text.](#)

NOTE: Selection and appointment of the MA or RA is subject to the procedure outlined in the [ISO/IEC Directives](#), Annex G and Annex H, and the RA policy in the ISO Supplement, Annex SN.

Annex(es) are included with this proposal (provide details)

[A draft \(comprising index, scope and introduction\) is enclosed](#)

Additional information/questions

[Click here to enter text.](#)